

Minutes of the 55th Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 2nd July 2015

(This document was finalised on 19th January 2016)

Present:

(CB)	Mrs Caroline Bulpett ²	
(CFL)	Dr Chris Lee ⁶	
(CG)	Dr Catherine Gaffard ²	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{3,4}	Secretary
(DK)	Dr Dirk Klugmann ⁴	
(EGN)	Dr Emily Norton ⁵	
(GM)	Mr Graeme Marlton ⁶	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁵	Chair
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ^{1,3}	
(ZL)	Dr Zhihong Li ²	

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

AMF	Atmospheric Measurement Facility
BADC	British Atmospheric Data Centre (now referred to as CEDA)
BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
DPW	David Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
GAP	Graham Parton (CEDA Data Scientist)
ISP	Internet Service Provider
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NLC	Noctilucent Cloud
PC	Personal Computer
TX	Transmitter
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

DK pointed out that his name should be removed from action item 46.5.3 since he had now left the Met Office. Stuart Matthews and Jacqueline Sugier are the appropriate people for dealing with the Laser Cloud Base Recorder data.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik Laser Cloud Base Recorder on the BADC.

COMPLETED

DAH reported on behalf of GAP (who was not at the meeting) that everything was now in place for the data to be delivered. Ag Stephens (from CEDA) has been chasing up the necessary people within the Met Office in order for this to go live.

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

DAH will give an update on this work relating to action item 51.6.1 in section 6c. No time will be devoted to the related action items 47.2.1 and 47.2.2 until this one has been completed.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

No time has been devoted to the action items 47.3.2, and 51.4.1 since the last meeting.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had established that the Met Office were happy for him to make the data available. GV clarified that it would be useful to have access to both the data files and the quick-look plots.

ACTION ITEM 53.2.2 DAH and JDE [Jon Eastment] to develop a business case for replacing the NERC MST Radar's transmitters with modern, solid-state units.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that he had submitted basic details of the requirements (rather than a business case) to GV in his capacity of NCAS Director of Observations.

ACTION ITEM 53.3.2 DAH to review security measures for the MST Radar site and to make improvements where necessary.

ONGOING

DAH reported that the outstanding task was to get some new signage for the site. GV recommended that DAH and LD should regularly walk around the perimeter fence to ensure that there are no breaches in it.

ACTION ITEM 53.4.2 GAP and DAH to determine a way of providing retrospectively-determined data reliability details in a machine-readable format.

ONGOING

DAH that there had been no progress on this since the last meeting.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

DAH gave a report on behalf of GAP, who was not at the meeting. Raw data from the AMF-NCAS (i.e. University of Manchester's) boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) continue to be transferred automatically to the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA). Long term observational data from 6th November 2013 to the end of 2014 have been added to the archive and catalogued.

There have been extensive modifications to the user interface for the CEDA catalogue. These have focused on getting users to the datasets that they are interested in as quickly as possible. Keyword fields are now available for all primary records and the search facility has been modified to improve the ranking and relevance of results. This work is ongoing and it is hoped to add geo-temporal search options in the near future. CEDA currently has two summer students and a year-in-industry student working on the catalogue content.

3b) Electricity

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units indicated brief (~1 s) input power problems on 3 occasions during the last 6 months: on 24th January 2015, on 4th February, and on 10th April.

The battery pack for the "TXD" unit failed a self test on 19th March 2015. Consequently, the transmitter for antenna section D shut down following a 6 s disruption to the mains supply on 29th March (a Sunday). DAH remotely restarted the transmitter when he spotted the problem on the following morning. The same transmitter shut down again in response to a brief (~1 s) disruption to the mains supply on 10th April. DAH remotely restarted the transmitter 2 hours later. LD installed a replacement battery pack later that morning. The original battery pack had been in operation since 2007.

3c) Telecommunications

The supplementary website - <http://www.mstrf.eclipse.co.uk> - which is hosted by the Facility's Internet Service Provider (ISP), was unavailable for a short period on the morning of 26th June 2015. This was a result of the ISP carrying out maintenance on their servers.

The DrayTek broadband router continues to be reliable. There has been no occasion during the past 6 months when it has needed to be power-cycled in order to restore a lost internet connection. EGN added that her router (the same model, following DAH's recommendation) was also continuing to provide re-

liable connections.

3d) Miscellaneous

The north-west corner of the antenna array was cleared of vegetation in the middle of February 2015. It had become overgrown by willow saplings. On this occasion the saplings were cut down. Previously they had been removed by scraping off the top-soil and everything embedded in it.

A fire officer from Aberystwyth University inspected the Facility's fire extinguishers on 20th February 2015.

Thirty four Environmental Science undergraduates from the University of Manchester visited the radar site on 8th April 2015. They were given presentations by GV, DAH, and DPW.

The activities of the "chemtrail" conspiracy theory community (some of whom "protested" outside the MST radar site in June 2014) continue to be mostly of the armchair variety. Nevertheless, small groups of them continue to target academic conferences such as the Solar Radiation Management Science 2015 conference, which was held in Cambridge during March 2015. Members of the wider community were predictably upset by Greenpeace's recent conclusion that "*chemtrails are an urban myth - a conspiracy theory with no conspiracy*". The full response can be found here - <http://www.greenpeace.org.uk/blog/other/greenpeace%E2%80%99s-view-%E2%80%98chemtrails%E2%80%99-20150313-0>.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There is nothing to report in connection with these sensors.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

On 30th March 2015 the readings of wind direction flipped by approximately 180° whilst the speed remained at around 5 m s⁻¹. Such an unrealistic pattern suggested that the wind vane sensor had developed a fault. Since the existing wind vane and anemometer had been in operation since 1995, DAH decided to replace them rather than to have them repaired. He and LD removed the old instruments on 8th April 2015 and LD installed the new ones on 22nd April. DAH initially delayed releasing the new data to CEDA until he had had a chance to establish whether the direction readings were realistic. There is potential for the wind vane to be installed back-to-front. The new data had not been made available at the time of the Experimenters' meeting.

DAH noted that the existing quick-look plots sometimes show unrealistically large gust speeds when the mean speed is near zero - see, for example, the plot for 11th January 2014. The source of the problem turns out to be the plotting software. It does not interpret gust wind speed factor (relative to the mean speed) values of "99.99" as missing datum values.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

The WXT510 instrument was found to be beyond repair in early January 2015. Since Vaisala have discontinued this model, it was replaced by a WXT520 on 3rd March 2015. DAH did not initially succeed in recording data using the existing connecting cable and (in-house written) acquisition software. It transpires that this was a result of the instrument's default data transmission rate being too high. DAH made appropriate adjustments when he next visited the site on 7th April and began to record the data.

DAH pointed out that he would need to make some changes to his formatting software before netCDF files could be released to CEDA. He asked whether it would be better to include the precipitation data together with the pressure, temperature, and humidity data or to store them in separate files as at present.

There was a mild consensus that no changes should be made.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

The data acquisition software, which runs on Windows PC “gaius”, stopped recording on 6 occasions: at 15:30 UT on 19th February 2015, at 15:14 on 27th March, at 15:14 on 19th April, at 15:20 on 8th May, at 15:37 on 20th May, and at 15:19 on 25th June. In each case there was a gap in the raw data until DAH spotted the problem and restarted the software.

4e) Sky-camera

A new camera, which will be officially referred to as Sky Camera 2, was installed on 1st December 2014. DAH initially planned to delay recording images until he had defined the necessary metadata, which can be embedded within the image files - see following section. However, since he had not had a chance to do this before the near-total solar eclipse of 20th March 2015, on 17th March he began to record the images regardless. Although the Sun was nowhere near the camera's field of view at the time of the eclipse, DAH was hopeful that the change in light levels would be apparent. Despite the fact that the radar site enjoyed clear skies on that morning, they were not. DAH reported that he and other members of the new Radar Advisory Group (which has replaced the NERC Atmospheric Radar Facilities Steering Committee) enjoyed naked-eye observations of the eclipse in Manchester whilst waiting for their inaugural meeting to begin. Images from the new camera will be made available through CEDA as soon as DAH has defined the metadata.

DAH reported that he was using sky-camera images as part of a display for a forthcoming Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) Open Day. He showed the example of a poster that illustrates the wide variety of possible atmospheric conditions. He has also created a number of time-lapse animations and showed the one for the morning of 7th September 2010. This reveals convection first being inhibited by and then breaking through a series of atmospheric “lids”.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

The camera had captured a low-elevation display of NLCs during the morning of 7th June 2015. Although the MST radar observed reasonably-long-lasting Mesosphere Summer Echoes on 24th June 2015, it has not been a good season so far.

DAH reported that he would release the images to CEDA as soon as he has automated the addition of metadata to the files. Images from digital cameras typically already include a large amount of metadata, e.g. relating to date/time of capture, shutter speed, focal length etc. The details can usually be viewed by right-clicking on the image and selecting “Properties”. DAH wants to include the additional parameters defined by the Dublin Core metadata standard. This serves a similar (albeit more-general) purpose to the CF metadata standard applied to netCDF data files. The same software tools can be used to add metadata to a range of file types including PNG (used for quick-look plots) and PDF (used for minutes of the Experimenters' meeting).

CG reported that since the Met Office became responsible for space weather, they have become interested in the mesospheric echoes observed by their South Uist radar. DAH reported that he had previously spoken to Mike Prottis (Met Office) about some unusual echoes that appeared to spread throughout the mesosphere. DAH thought that the echoes were probably a result of interference in this particular case since they were observed at all altitudes.

4g) MST Radar

CB began this section by reporting data quality monitoring statistics. The EUCOS data show a small step reduction in the daily number of observations submitted in late September 2014. The reason for this is unknown. CG recommended checking if other wind-profilers were affected. There were also a number of individual days on which the number of observations submitted was significantly below normal. The

most significant of these was around 11th May 2015, when fewer than 15% of the usual number were submitted. There were no known internet issues at this time - see section 3c. The model-comparison statistics show that the daily root mean square mean wind differences only exceeded the 5 m s^{-1} EUCOS upper limit on a few occasions. As usual, the daily root mean square direction differences showed more variability. The monthly values of “availability” and “timeliness” were above 99% for the past 6 months.

CB next presented the comparison statistics against the Met Office's UKV model. The monthly profiles are closely comparable for both the MST radar and radiosonde winds. This indicates good data quality. There have been no significant changes since the previous reporting period. CFL thought that the biases between model and observation winds appear to have reduced. DK speculated that this might reflect an improvement in the model. CG commented that the statistics for the South Uist radar showed the opposite pattern of speed biases seen for the Aberystwyth radar, i.e. a slightly negative bias in the troposphere and a slightly positive bias in the lower stratosphere. However, this is only seen for the high mode. CG wondered whether this could reflect a slight range gating error since the receiver is only sampled at 500 m intervals in the high mode. CFL commented that the AMF-NCAS BLWP had suffered from height problems, which were eventually traced to an error in the configuration file.

DAH then gave a technical report on the MST radar's performance. The transmitter for antenna section B was out of action on 4 occasions owing to a blown fuse: starting on 1st February 2015, 11th April, 27th April, and 14th May. It remained out of action for between 24 and 72 hours on each occasion. The transmitter for antenna section C was similarly out of action on 4 occasions: starting on 3rd February 2015, on 22nd April, on 3rd May, and on 17th June. The transmitter for antenna section D was out of action only once for this reason starting on 11th May. However, it was out of action on 2 occasions owing to a faulty battery pack (see section 3b): on 29th March 2015, and on 10th April.

The radar suffered intermittently from a raised noise floor between 23rd and 26th January 2015. This was mostly apparent in the m-mode observations. The cause of this problem is not known although DAH speculates that it is associated with the cold outside conditions. The radar suffered from interference for approximately an hour on 2 occasions: on 13th and 26th June 2015. This led to brief reductions in useful altitude coverage.

The radar was stopped twice (for approximate 20 minutes each) on 31st March 2015 to allow LD to replace beam steering unit 11. It was found to be burnt out inside, which would explain why it had become unresponsive. LD suspects that this was a result of water ingress and the second radar stoppage was to allow him to water proof the cable.

5. Guest Instrument Report

EGN gave a report on the AMF-NCAS BLWP covering the last 6 months. A new wooden-framed clutter screen was constructed at Cardington on 28th February 2015 by a local builder. The frame of the previous screen was composed of scaffold poles that had been left at the site from a previous project. The new screen looks a bit odd, but has proved to be more effective than its predecessor. Clutter was primarily seen at a range of 2 - 3 km and so was probably not caused by the nearby hangars. The new screen blew over as a result of strong winds on 30 March 2015. Repairs were carried out on 28th April, principally by adding extra bracing and fixing the mesh.

The BLWP observations made on 9th June 2015 were so unusual that they were initially assumed to be the result of an instrument problem. They are now being investigated for their scientific interest. Attention has been focused on a region of moderate downward velocities ($\sim 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and large spectral widths. This combination is typically associated with precipitation echoes. Moreover, the Halo Doppler lidar observations suggest that precipitation is occurring during at least some of the period of interest. The surface temperature and visibility both showed reductions. Nevertheless, no rain was detected at

ground level and the BLWP signal powers did not show the enhancement typically associated with precipitation echoes. CFL commented that the Degreane software might be confused by the fact the echoes have a Gaussian spectral form since it is looking for non-Gaussian precipitation echoes. CG suggested looking at the fields of total liquid water content.

The latest BLWP data can now be viewed through the Met Office's website - <http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/weather/ewinprof/profiler/cardington>. Data are now being transferred every 15 minutes rather than every hour. Quick-look plots can also be accessed through the AMF's live data page - <https://ncas.ac.uk/index.php/en/about-amf/336-amf-main-category/amf-live-data>. This interface allows the data to be searched on a campaign/deployment basis.

A new Campbell Scientific CS135 laser Ceilometer was added to BLWP setup in May 2015. The BLWP software can incorporate the ceilometer data into its ".dat" file. This will allow cloud base altitudes to be viewed in real time together with the wind profile data.

The BLWP is currently being used to study the morning transition. Later in the year it will be deployed to Met Office's Camborne site for an intercomparison with their own BLWP. Thereafter it be operated at Heathrow as part of a year long fog experiment.

GV gave a brief report on the other University of Manchester instruments. He is interested in using the Raman lidar at Capel Dewi to study free tropospheric aerosol. Not much has been published on this. The lidar has previously seen aerosols from as far afield as Canada (as the result of biomass burning). DPW has collected lots of new data. It was reported at the previous Experimenters' meeting that the Elight lidar had nearly been fixed. However, despite DPW having worked on it, it is no closer to being back in working order. The SAOZ instrument has also suffered from problems and has been sent back to the manufacturer in France for repairs.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) MST Radar and BLWP wind comparison - CFL

CFL recently made a study of the accuracy of MST radar winds. This made use of data from over a hundred radiosondes that were launched from the radar site. Although the two sets of measurements were generally well-matched, the mean differences between the speeds reveals an altitude-dependent bias. Moreover, the profile of (time) mean radar-derived vertical velocity has a similar "S" shape. This suggests that the differences in speed are real and that they are the result of mountain wave activity. This work has already been published - <http://www.atmos-meas-tech.net/7/3113/2014/amt-7-3113-2014.html>.

CFL has now extended the work to compare MST radar and BLWP winds. When comparing vertical velocities, it is important to disregard those BLWP measurements that correspond to hydrometeor echoes. Their vertical velocities represent hydrometeor fall speeds rather than the vertical wind. The Degreane processing software applies various tests to distinguish between hydrometeor and clear air echoes. Although these appear to be quite effective, the apparent availability of a small number of clear air echoes at the higher altitudes (from which the clear air echoes are typically too weak to detect) suggests that hydrometeor echoes are occasionally mis-classified. Despite these measures, there are significant differences between the profiles of (time) mean vertical velocities from the BLWP and MST radar.

CFL wondered whether the assumption that clear air radar return signals have a Gaussian spectral form might contribute to the differences. Although this is a good assumption for BLWP signals, it's only a rough approximation for MST radar signals. It becomes increasingly valid as consecutive spectra are averaged together. Although this reduces the number of data points available for comparison, it makes the comparison more robust. Nevertheless, the BLWP vertical velocities still have a noticeable positive

bias relative to those from the MST radar.

CFL has ruled out a number of potential reasons for the differences. If the hydrometeor scatter signals were contaminating the BLWP dataset, the bias would be expected to be negative. Moreover, this effect would be confined to the higher altitudes. If the BLWP's vertical beam were aligned slightly off-vertical, the sign of the vertical velocity differences would be expected to depend on the horizontal wind direction. They do not. If the two instruments were measuring different wind fields, the MST radar vertical velocities derived from complementary off-vertical beams would be expected to differ from those derived from vertical beams. They do not. Degreane's BLWP clutter rejection algorithm cannot be responsible since, by default, it is not applied to the vertical beam (CFL had only just discovered this). The possibility of different scattering mechanisms being responsible for the radar returns seen by the two instruments is avoided by rejecting non-Gaussian signals.

CFL has also compared the horizontal winds. The profiles of the mean differences between radar and radiosonde wind speeds are similar for the MST and BLWP data. However, there are systematic differences between the data from the two radars. The magnitude of the differences increases with increasing speed. There's also a slight dependence on altitude, which would be consistent with a slight ($\sim 1^\circ$) error in BLWP pointing direction. GV thought it should be possible to see such an error from the spirit levels on the antenna panels. DK wondered whether it could be a result of the two radars sampling different scales of turbulence. He thought it would be interesting to compare data from two BLWPs that are operated side by side.

6b) Measuring turbulence with adapted radiosondes and comparison with the NERC MST radar - GM

GM's PhD work has involved investigating the potential of modified radiosondes to measure turbulence intensity. This is based on the principle that a change in wind speed or direction will cause a radiosonde to swing beneath its balloon. The amplitude of the swings will depend on the frequency and the magnitude of the changes and can be inferred from the acceleration experienced by the radiosonde. RS92 radiosondes have been adapted to carry 3-axis accelerometers for this purpose. The first intercomparisons were made against data from a Doppler lidar and so were confined to the boundary layer - <http://scitation.aip.org/content/aip/journal/rsi/86/1/10.1063/1.4905529>. A recent campaign at the MST radar site has allowed intercomparisons to be extended to higher altitudes. Between January and April 2015, 18 adapted radiosondes were launched during 3 2-day periods.

For this presentation GM focused on MST radar beam-broadening corrected spectral widths derived from 6° off-vertical beams. He has previously used vertical beam data. In one case study, from 4th March 2015, low values of aspect sensitivity and enhanced values of corrected spectral width were found through most of the core of the jet. The standard deviation of acceleration also showed enhanced values across this region. Looking at the data from all radiosondes and using 1.5 km altitude bins, there is a broad positive correlation between corrected spectral widths and the standard deviation of acceleration. GM has calculated radar eddy dissipation rates using two methods. The first requires knowledge of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency. It results in a weak correlation with the standard deviation of acceleration. The second uses information about the radar pulse volume, using the method of Labitt (Coordinated radar and aircraft observations of turbulence, Massachusetts Institute of Technology Technical report, 1981). This gives a stronger linear relationship, although the radar values are an order of magnitude smaller than given by the first method. A third method is based on the assumption of a $-5/3$ slope Kolmogorov spectrum. However, this requires knowledge of the inner and outer length scales and it is not obvious what value should be used for the latter.

6b) Improving Theta S/Theta Effective Correction - DAH

The aspect sensitivity of radar returns is a measure of how quickly the radar return signal power decreases as the radar beam is steered away from the vertical. Where turbulence fills a radar observation

volume, the refractive index irregularities that cause backscatter are expected to be isotropic. The aspect sensitivity is therefore expected to be low, since the irregularities will look the same irrespective of the angle at which they are viewed. However, since it is not known for how long refractive index irregularities remain isotropic after turbulence has ceased, near-zero aspect sensitivity cannot necessarily be interpreted as indicating the presence of active turbulence.

One of the consequences of aspect sensitivity is that the zenith angle of an off-vertical radar beam will be slightly closer to the zenith than the nominal angle suggests. A correction factor, derived from the ratio of radar return signal powers at two zenith angles, must be applied to the horizontal wind speed in order to compensate for this.

The wind speed compensation factor is currently calculated on a cycle by cycle basis. It is based on the signal power averaged over all four 6.0° off-vertical beams and on the signal power from a single 4.2° off-vertical beam. DAH had already demonstrated that this factor was noisy and that a certain degree of time averaging is required (approximately 30 minutes is recommended). He had also demonstrated that even after averaging, there can be significant variations in signal power between off-vertical beams with the same zenith angle but different azimuth angles. This suggests that it would be better to make use of all four 4.2° off-vertical beams rather than the single one used at present. However, a better way might be to calculate the wind speed compensation factor based on observations made in the vertical direction rather than at 4.2° off-vertical. Six vertical beam dwells are already included in the standard observation cycle. Although DAH had concluded that this would lead to an overcompensation when he first examined this subject as a PhD student, he now thinks that the difference might not be so great. He pointed out that there is a highly non-linear relationship between the signal power ratio and the θ_s measure of aspect sensitivity. Consequently when the value of θ_s is less than 10°, small changes in the signal power ratio have apparently large effects on the value of θ_s . It is much better to consider the effective (zenith) pointing angle or the wind speed compensation factor, both of which have a quasi linear dependence on the signal power ratio. For this purpose, DAH has begun to look at the observations made using all available beam pointing directions during March 2011.

6d) Wind profiler backscatter signal monitoring - CG

At present, the Met Office only make use of the wind data from wind-profiling radars. There are a number of potential benefits for taking the backscattered signal power into consideration. For a start, this would improve the scope for detecting instrument performance issues. It would also provide an indirect way to assess the temperature and humidity fields seen in the UKV model and would be a first step towards assimilating the data. However, there are 3 potential backscattering mechanisms (i.e. turbulent/Bragg scatter, Fresnel reflection/scatter, and Rayleigh scatter) to be taken into consideration. It might be necessary to operate additional instruments (such as a ceilometer and/or a cloud radar) alongside a wind-profiling radar in order to determine where and when to apply each one.

The Met Office's UKV model is run at 1.5 km horizontal resolution and uses a 3D-Var data assimilation scheme on a 3 hourly cycle. The "background field" is the short-term forecast from the previous cycle and is available at hourly intervals (hourly-cycling 4D-Var is under development; this will give updates to the background field at 10 minute intervals). The values of temperature, pressure, and humidity are used to calculate the square of the vertical gradient of potential refractive. This is then compared with the range-squared-corrected radar signal-to-noise ratio, which it is expected to influence for two of the backscattering mechanisms. This comparison has been made on an hourly basis since September 2014 for the Camborne, Dunkeswell, Isle of Man, and Wattisham BLWPs. This has given encouraging results for a first attempt. The top of the boundary layer typically shows up clearly in both the model and observation fields. However, features at higher altitudes are not always so well matched. This is probably partly because the BLWPs lack the sensitivity to see clear air patterns above the first few kilometres of the atmosphere. In general, the comparisons are less good for the low mode observations than for the high mode. This is perhaps because the vertical resolution of the low mode observations is higher than

that of the model (GV wondered whether the resolution of the observations could be degraded before comparisons are made). Moreover, the comparisons are poor under precipitation conditions. This is to be expected since the refractive index field has no relevance to the Rayleigh scatter from hydrometeors.

6e) 94 GHz Doppler Radar Profiler: Status of Development - DK

The RAL Millimetre Wave Technology group have been developing a semiconductor-based cloud radar for a number of years. The earliest model operated at 75 GHz, but later ones have shifted to 94 GHz. The instrument does not yet have Doppler capability, which is seen as being increasingly important. DK has been responsible for updating the radio frequency design. This has involved making simplifications, where possible, and maximising the use of in-house designed/built (as opposed to third party) components. These changes are aimed at making the instrument cheaper and more reliable. For example, the number of oscillators required has been reduced from three to one. This reduces the impact of drifts. It will also allow for the introduction of Doppler capability.

The first step in the redesign has been to set up a simplified demonstrator unit, which operates at around 1 GHz. This will allow the new in-house modules to be tested. One of the novel features of the new system is that the desired radio signal can be synthesised rather than being generated by a voltage controlled oscillator. However, this has been found to generate spurious frequency components outside of the main band. Band pass filtering will be needed to avoid these contributions. DK is currently assessing different amplifier modules.

7. Any Other Business

The date of the next Experimenters' meeting was provisionally set for 3rd week of January 2016.